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Donor Dependency, Embeddedness and Organizational Structure of Civil Society: An Analysis of a Global Sample of Actors Active in the Field of Corporate Accountability

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ABSTRACT

Faced with the growing influence of multinational corporations on global politics and economy, civil society organizations play an increasing role in holding corporations accountable for human rights violations and environmental degradation. However, the effectiveness of global civil society in this role and the consequences of power dynamics between donors and funded organizations for corporate accountability (CA) strategies are still disputed. This article uses original data on 290 civil society actors to examine the role of funding sources for the organizations' repertoires and aims. The main findings reveal that receiving funding from state or government authorities reduces the probability of using contentious strategies, whereas funding from charities has no such effect. Funding from state or government authorities also diminishes the likelihood of organizations to pursue more radical claims such as economic reforms. Such funding, then, becomes an impediment to seeking structural change and to employing more radical repertoires. The article concludes that CA initiatives, while using the tools and resources that the current legal, economic and political system provides, can, at least potentially, fail to have the intended effect. Rather than challenging power and provoking structural change, they can contribute to cementing existing power structures and legitimizing dominant discourses.

1 | Introduction

Corporations increasingly exert influence over political decision-making, raising concerns about democratic accountability and regulatory capture (Katelouzou and Zumbansen 2020; Zumbansen and Katelouzou 2020; Crouch et al. 2016; Korten 1995; Crouch 2011). In response, many scholars, despite the evident imbalance of power, turn to civil society to expose corporate abuses, advocate for policy change and hold corporations accountable (Reinecke and Donaghey 2023; Saage-Maaß et al. 2021; Payne et al. 2020; Reinecke and Donaghey 2015; Bieri

2013; Dale 2011). Notably Keck and Sikkink's (1998) seminal work on transnational advocacy networks (TANs) and the short-lived alter-globalization movement in the early 2000s prompted a turn in research on global civil society and transnational social movements as emerging counter-forces to neoliberal globalization and the borderless power of its main proponents and agents (della Porta 2007; della Porta and Tarrow 2004; Smith and Johnston 2002; Khagram et al. 2002; Klein 1999). However, despite the growing contention surrounding corporations, the tangible impact of activism on corporate behaviour remains to be demonstrated (Davis et al. 2022). Although many scholars and

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practitioners posit the crucial role of civil society in holding corporations accountable, the (potential) lack of effectiveness of their endeavours and the consequences of power relations between donors and organizations have begun to attract public and scholarly attention. This is not a purely academic discussion; concerns frequently surface in public debates, especially when organizations that receive substantial government or philanthropic funding, such as Oxfam or Greenpeace, engage in confrontational discourse or direct action. Broader political controversies around funding schemes like USAID or philanthropic networks like the Open Society Foundation further underscore the need to understand how external funding shapes the strategies, legitimacy and perceived autonomy of civil society actors. In the field of corporate accountability (CA), questions surrounding the role of funding are particularly intriguing, as many, if not most, organizations depend on grants by philanthropies and charities that often flow from the very money their founders earned with corporate enterprises. For instance, will organizations funded by the FORD Foundation (one of the main funders of CA initiatives, whereas FORD itself was accused of numerous human rights abuses; Payne et al. 2020) struggle in the same way and with similar goals as organizations funded by Rosa Luxemburg Foundation, another major donor in the field and the political foundation of the German Left party? Such examples raise broader questions about the extent to which structural characteristics and funding configurations influence the strategies, goals and transformative potential of civil society actors. What is the relationship between different structural characteristics of civil society actors and the way they fight for their causes? How does their funding shape the aims and the repertoires of the actors involved? What role does their embeddedness in networks play? Ultimately, what are impediments to the ability of civil society to provoke structural change?

Research has shown that funding dependence, whether on authorities or charities, can compromise the autonomy and activities of civil society organizations (Banks et al. 2015; Edwards and Hulme 1996). Still, it remains unclear how these dynamics unfold in different organizational settings and strategic contexts. Studies suggest that access to stable funding may steer organizations toward moderation, whereas resource scarcity can incentivize more radical or confrontational tactics (Dauvergne and LeBaron 2014; Yaziji and Doh 2013; Ebrahim 2003). However, these patterns have rarely been examined through comprehensive comparative analysis grounded in global data. Rather, existing scholarship on civil society and funding often relied on conceptual discussions or analyses of a small number of large, western NGOs, limiting its capacity to account for structural variation across the broader organizational landscape (e.g., Davies 2019). This gap is particularly pronounced in the field of CA, where the structural conditions under which civil society actors operate and the influence of funding, networks and organizational form, remain understudied.

We aim to fill these gaps through a theory-driven rigorous analysis of a large number of civil society actors, both formally and informally organized (henceforth ‘organizations’)—including social movements, trade unions, NGOs and TANs—active in or connected to the field of CA, from across the globe. These organizations constitute the unit of analysis of the dataset and of the present study. Our study focuses on how these actors struggle for CA by analysing what Tilly and Tarrow (2006) call ‘claim-

making repertoires’ (p. 16) and analyses what factors influence the choice to engage in conventional or unconventional actions.

To do so and to answer the questions formulated above, we analyse an original dataset that records characteristics of a sample of 290 civil society actors. The ‘Civil Society Active in Corporate Accountability Dataset’ was constructed following the action organization analysis (AOE) approach and represents a network of organizations active in the area of CA (Rammelt 2024).

The article is organized in four sections. In the first section, we introduce the main epistemological and conceptual sources, develop our theory-driven framework of analysis and propose our hypotheses. The second section presents the dataset, the main variables and our methodological approach. In the third and fourth sections, we present and discuss the findings of our research. The conclusion summarizes the main results and identifies weaknesses in the presented research and avenues for further research.

2 | Existing Scholarship—CA, Global Civil Society and Donor Dependence

2.1 | CA and Global Civil Society

One of civil society’s main roles is to hold influential actors accountable (Anheier et al. 2001; Warkentin and Mingst 2000; Lipschutz 1992). There is no unanimous definition of ‘global civil society’; some analysts define it as the collective of international nongovernmental organizations worldwide, whereas others use the term more narrowly to refer specifically to nongovernmental actors engaging with global governance institutions or conceptualize it as a space for negotiating a (global) social contract (Selchow 2010). The civil society we analyse in this article is to a greater or lesser extent involved in responding to social problems caused by corporate activities and part of the global CA movement. Notably in arenas where governmental responses are not forthcoming—such as the field of climate and sustainability governance, where questions on the role of corporations are highly contentious—non-state actors, not least civil society, assume a crucial role (Hale 2020; Chan et al. 2019). Within this arena, a range of actors, ranging from established large professional NGOs like Greenpeace and the World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF) to international networks like Friends of the Earth (FoE) or newer, more decentralized movements, have launched campaigns to hold corporations accountable for environmental wrongdoings. Such actors target corporations in different ways and for different reasons: Greenpeace has challenged fossil fuel companies such as Shell and ExxonMobil through direct action and information campaigns; FoE engaged in major boycott campaigns against different corporations, notably in the agribusiness; and others mobilizes public opinion and political pressure on both governments and major polluters like automotive and energy firms. These actions fall within the broader field of CA as they demand systemic change in corporate behaviour and address grievances generated by corporations’ disregard for human rights and the environment. Such actors also fund their activities in different ways: organizations like WWF and Greenpeace mostly rely on individual donations and charity grants, whereas others depend on funding from authorities or membership fees. Smaller

community projects in the Global South often address local concerns but depend on money from foreign donors.

Scholarship has demonstrated that global civil society do exert pressure on corporations (Reinecke and Donaghey 2023; Saage-Maaß et al. 2021; Payne et al. 2020; Reinecke and Donaghey 2015; Bieri 2013; Dale 2011). A variety of potential actions to hold corporations accountable have been catalogued (Birchall 2020), ranging from public pressure via information (including research and counter-accounting, or exposing corporate abuses) and advocacy campaigns (including the struggle for labour and environmental protection), to supporting victims of human rights abuses via humanitarian or legal support and engaging legal action, notably via strategic litigations. Taking the example of CA-related organizations in the field of sustainability, one notices that they employ different repertoires, ranging from lobbying and strategic litigation (WWF) to boycotts (FoE) and mass protest (Greenpeace).

Attempts to change corporate behaviour can also include collaborations between civil society organizations and corporations, persuasion or shareholder activism (Dahan et al. 2010; Åhlström and Sjöström 2005). International connections and networks were key to Keck and Sikkink's (1998) 'boomerang effect', but they were also seen as frequently provoking organizational change, notably a more professional and efficient organizational structure. It is reasonable to assume that also a normative alignment would take place, in which organizations adapt their goals to fit the international standards or principles espoused by international actors and donors. In their struggle, organizations also often form coalitions with 'elite allies' like churches and politicians (Reinecke and Donaghey 2015; Dale 2011; Keck and Sikkink 1998). Embeddedness, international or domestic, can then be seen as both a requirement for efficient activism and an impediment to more radical activism, in terms of repertoires and goals. Corporations have responded to the pressure exerted by civil society and other stakeholders by altering the discourses: They legitimize and consolidate their power by shifting the focus on discursive strategies such as CSR, sustainability or economic growth and prosperity, public confessions, or by pursuing the promotion of voluntary principles (Balsiger 2018; Banerjee and Bonnefous 2011; Banerjee 2008). However, such initiatives are widely seen to have failed to deliver on their promises (Li and Soule 2022; Yan and Zhang 2020; Locke 2013; Zumbansen 2006). A prime example of such responses are 'sustainability efforts' within some of the most polluting industries; Shell's 'sustainability reports' gained a prominent status, not only in activist circles, for an effort to distract the public from Shell's continued fossil fuel extraction and environmental and human rights violations, notably in the Niger Delta. As corporations increasingly become the dominant actors—controlling means, resources and government policies, as well as the discourse—mobilizations that utilize the existing legal and economic framework in their struggles that become more professional and embedded in professional networks risk contributing to the status quo rather than provoking structural change (Khoury and Whyte 2017).

2.2 | Donor-Civil Society Relations

The relation between civil society's funding sources and their actions has been studied in various domains, but a systematic study on the field of CA is still missing. Edwards and

Hulme (1996) found that a dependence on funding stemming from different authorities compromised the performance and legitimacy of development NGOs; nearly 20 years later, Banks et al. (2015) revisited this argument, now focusing on the question of whether changes in the donor environment enabled NGOs to better contest hegemonic corporate interests (p. 707). They found that the current donor environment—notably the increased focus on results, on moderating their positions and on professionalization—leads to a situation in which NGOs were as compromised as the NGOs dependent on funding from authorities (p. 709). These findings are in line with other studies describing the relationship between donors and NGOs as one of control and patronage toward donors, who control the flow of funds, leading to discrepancies between local needs and available resources (Reith 2010; Bob 2005; Ebrahim 2003). This trend has also been noticed by state authorities themselves: The Prime Minister's Office of Finland (2020) observed that developments in the funding of civil society and in particular of NGOs have weakened the ability of organizations to act as initiators of social reforms and argued that the civil society's dependence on grant makers must be reduced. Further, most non-state donors operate with little transparency (Morcillo Laiz 2020) and without any democratic legitimacy, further warranting the need to study their interactions with civil society actors. Focusing on processes internal to NGOs, such as group processes that affect the tactics, target selection and interactions with targeted firms, Yaziji and Doh (2009) also found that radical NGOs are likely to be smaller and attract fewer resources. Saunders and Roth (2019) find that the dependence on donors provokes organizations outsized answerability to the funders. Organizations hence become more professional and connected to other actors but risk losing sight of their constituency and their initial goals and are likely to adopt repertoires that are sanctioned by donors and other, notably international, actors.

Cross- or transnational embeddedness can potentially increase access to funding by organizations at the risk of needing to conform to 'best practices' and rules of engagement as established by big INGOs, IOs and their donors; for example, many TANs will condition partnership upon the renouncement from violent repertoires (Grosescu 2025; Greenwood-Reeves 2023).

To sum it up, competition for resources, network access and pressure to deliver short-term results impacts the framing and choice of repertoires of organizations. By and large, a trend toward de-radicalization (in terms of both repertoires and frames) can be observed; civil society, notably the one that challenges corporations, has become less contentious. As more and more civil society actors started collaborating directly with big business, they increasingly started advocating for business-friendly solutions (Dauvergne and LeBaron 2014). This observation is particularly important for debates on CA, which are traditionally divided between those that advocate for voluntary approaches to CA and those that insist on binding legal obligations (Ruggie 2018). In these debates, different 'soft' business-friendly solutions, including advocacy for responsibility (rather than enforceable accountability), voluntary approaches to CA, industry-internal certification standards and, not least, the general exclusion of harder alternatives, notably economic reforms, are frequently criticized for their lack of effectiveness (de Boer 2021; Schilling-Vacaflor and Lenschow 2023; Schilling-Vacaflor et al. 2021; Morgera 2020; Baars 2018).

On the basis of this body of work, we formulate six hypotheses regarding the effect of funding, professionalization and embeddedness on the organization's repertoire and goals.

Hypothesis 1. *Organizations that receive funding from authorities are less likely to engage in contentious activities than organizations that do not receive such funding.*

Hypothesis 2. *Organizations that receive funding from charities are less likely to engage in contentious activities compared to organizations that do not receive such funding.*

Hypothesis 3. *Organizations that receive funding from authorities are less likely to pursue a reform of the economic system.*

Hypothesis 4. *Organizations that receive funding from charities are less likely to pursue a reform of the economic system.*

Hypothesis 5. *Organizations that have a higher degree of professionalization are less likely to engage in contentious repertoires compared to organizations with a lower degree of professionalization.*

Hypothesis 6. *Organizations that are more embedded are less likely to engage in contentious repertoires compared to organizations that are not embedded.*

3 | Data and Methods

3.1 | Data Structure and Retrieval

The analysis relies on original data collected as part of the 'Civil Society Active in Corporate Accountability' database (Rammelt 2024). Data collection followed an AOE approach (Kousis et al. 2018). We identified hub-websites through the free version of the Global Civil Society Database, which provides 'profiles of non-profit organizations working worldwide in all fields of activity' (Global Civil Society Database 2025). The database is maintained by the Union of International Associations, a Brussels based non-profit independent research institute, best known for its flagship publication 'Yearbook of International Organizations'. Filtering for 'CA' and 'corporate justice', four hub-websites (and hub-organizations) were identified: African Coalition for Corporate Accountability, International Corporate Accountability Roundtable, Corporate Accountability International and European Coalition for Corporate Justice. Hub-websites constitute the initial nodes of the network. Subsequently, 195 links to organizations that were listed as 'partners' or 'network' were extracted from these hub-websites. In the third step, the 'about' sections¹ of these partner websites were scanned for references to CA and corporate justice. In the fourth step, links to partner websites from the websites that contained references to these terms were extracted, resulting in an additional 677 identified partners. Hence, the four hub-organizations listed in total 195 partners, and these 195 organizations contained links to 677 of their partners that included in the 'about' sections references to CA and corporate justice. This means that all organizations in the sample are either clearly active in the field under study or are directly related to an organization that is active in the field. This full network sampling allowed for a clear definition of network

boundaries. In so doing, a global sample of formal and informal organizations active in the field of CA was identified. The unit of analysis is then organizations (both formal and informal). Link extraction resulted in a sample of 876 websites that allowed for the mapping and systematic analysis of comparable cross-national data of a variety of types of organizations. Through this data collection procedure, methodological biases based on the analysis of existing media content (such as Protest Event Analysis [PEA] or Political Claims Analysis) could be limited by targeting the source rather than the representation. Consequently, the dataset is composed of an unmediated population of organizations that are both influential in the public discourse and informal, marginal or grassroots groups. In this regard, the only limitation is that the data are limited to organizations that have an online presence and are discoverable.

In the final step, a random sample of organizational websites was drawn by assigning each organization a number with a (pseudo-)random number generator. In total, 290 websites were drawn and subsequently had their characteristics coded. A power analysis was conducted to determine that this sample size is sufficient to detect a moderate effect ($OR = 2.3$) with 0.8 power at the alpha level of 0.05. The data were collected between October 2022 and April 2023 and, as such, provide a snapshot of the publicly available data at that moment. To verify the reliability of the data, we repeated the coding of the characteristics used in this analysis for a random 10% of organizations and achieved 98% consistency.

Although we do not claim that the dataset is fully representative of the global population of organizations due to the sampling methodology based on the hub-websites, it does provide a comprehensive exploratory sample, at least for organizations located in Africa, Europe and North America (Table 1). The geographic composition of the sample is consistent with existing datasets on civil society, such as in the Humanitarian Organizations Database (HOD), compiled by Egger and Schopper (2022), wherein eight countries (six of them in North America and Europe, one in Africa and one in Asia) account for more than 40% of all organizations included in the sample. Africa has become the epicentre of human rights issues resulting from corporate activities (Olawuyi 2015), whereas most transnational corporations (TNCs) are headquartered in Europe and North America. The domination of organizations from Africa (23% of organizations), Europe (29%) and North America (28%) in our dataset lends credibility to its geographical representativeness. Further, what is generally referred to as 'global civil society' is in fact a network dominated by the most powerful nations (Khoury and Whyte 2017, 162), and, at first glance, the distribution of cases in the present sample (in pure numbers, without taking into account actual power relations between the organizations) can be understood as an empirical representation of this domination.

Although the merits of the data collection method we used are clear (including data collection on a global network of organizations by means of desk research, and an easy and accessible codebook and dataset), a number of caveats should be pointed out. First, although the data grasps a network of organizations, there are also other active networks of organizations. The sample we analysed is the extended network of the four TNCs that were identified through the Global Civil Society Database. Additionally, the network and the extended network

TABLE 1 | Distribution across regions.

Region	Africa	Asia	Australia	Europe	Latin America	North America	Global ^a
Count	68	20	3	83	35	80	1
Percentage	23.4	6.9	1.0	28.6	12.1	27.6	0.3

^aGlobal Campaign to Reclaim Peoples Sovereignty, Dismantle Corporate Power and Stop Impunity.

only include partners that were directly mentioned or linked, whereas theoretically organizations may also collaborate with other groups, networks and organizations that are not publicly acknowledged or not discoverable online. This is probably not the case for donors, as most donors require public acknowledgment of their funding. Second, quantifying the data derived from the qualitative analysis always implies a certain level of simplification. Subtle differences between, among other possibilities, the visions of the organizations in question can remain hidden. Third, organizations might describe their mission, vision and activities on their websites (e.g., to comply with funding requirements) in a certain way, while acting differently, based on different motivations in reality. However, most of these limitations are to be encountered with other methods that are less comprehensive or affected by additional biases.

3.2 | Key Variables and Coding Rules

The data cover both structural/organizational information and information pertaining to the more subjective dimensions of activities (such as aims and repertoires) and allow for systematic and cross-national analyses. The classifications are based on common practices in the use of AOE and PEA.

Activities the organizations engage in were coded on the basis of the information provided on the organizations' websites (e.g., 'What we do' sections) and in annual reports. Both current and past activities (if mentioned) were recorded. The codebook allows for the coding of all activities and to capture the diversity in the activities. Activities are coded as a set of binary variables, where 1 represents the presence of a given activity type in the self-presentation of organizations, and 0 otherwise. 'Contentious repertoires' is coded as 1 if the organization engages in at least one of the three contentious activity types: occupation and blockades, confrontational activities or demonstrative activities. Funding was coded on the basis of the information provided on the website and in annual/financial reports. 'Funding from authorities' was coded as 1 if the organization declared that they receive funding from authorities, hence different authorities and agencies (including different state agencies, such as ministries, government-administered agencies or supranational organizations such as the European Union and African Union). 'Charity funding' was coded if the organization declared funding from charities or philanthropic organizations. In the absence of annual/financial reports or acknowledgments on the website (e.g., 'funded by the European Union' or 'We thank the foundation for their generous support') existing logos of charities or government agencies were used instead for coding purposes.

We recorded the aims organizations mentioned as measures they undertake to achieve their goals as follows. The 'reform the economic system' route was coded if the organization tries to achieve their goals by reforming the economic system. For example, the sentence 'We exist to organize our members into a more powerful and united force, in order to accelerate the transition of our economic system from capitalism to a solidarity economy' as stated on the website of the New Economy Coalition would be considered evidence of the organization pursuing economic reform.

Eight organizational features were coded as indicators of professionalization and formalization. This variable included the following organizational features: annual/financial reports, board of directors, constitution, donation option, 'get involved', news section/pressroom/newsletter, organizational chart, volunteering possibilities. These features reflect widely recognized dimensions of professionalization in both nonprofit and movement organizations, such as formal hierarchy, routinized practices and resource mobilization channels (McCarthy and Zald 1977; Staggenborg 1988; Hwang and Powell 2009). The variable 'professionalization' ranges from 0 to 8. Relational and networking data of organizations were also collected; the variable 'embeddedness' was coded if the organization is either part of an umbrella organization or platform or has partners.²

Among these variables, the operationalization of 'contentious repertoires' warrants particular clarification. To capture whether an organization engaged in any such activity, we combined occupations and blockades, confrontational actions and demonstrative activities into a single binary indicator. This decision is rooted in the literature on contentious politics, which identifies such practices as part of the shared repertoire of extra-institutional strategies used to challenge dominant actors (Tilly and Tarrow 2006; McAdam et al. 2001). These repertoires have been classified in various ways: Some scholars emphasize public perceptions of disruption or harm, referring to them as 'extreme' actions (Feinberg et al. 2020), whereas others define them based on their deviation from institutionalized and conventional forms of participation, such as lobbying or education (della Porta and Diani 1999). Grouping them under the category of contentious repertoires is analytically appropriate, as they fall outside both conventional modes of political participation and formalized or institutionalized mechanisms of interest representation. In addition to models predicting the contentious activities index, we present supplementary models predicting each of the three types of activities (occupations and blockades, confrontational actions and demonstrative activities) separately.

Distributions of all constructed variables, expressed as proportions of positive values of all binary indicators, as well as the

TABLE 2 | Summary statistics of all variables included in analyses.

Variable	Count	Proportion
Contentious	87	0.300
Funding: Authorities	104	0.359
Funding: Charities	156	0.538
High embeddedness	173	0.597
Route: Economic reform	95	0.328
	Mean	Standard deviation
Professionalization (0–8)	3.290	2.040

Note: $N = 290$ organizations.

mean and standard deviation of the professionalization scale, are provided in Table 2. According to these descriptives, 30% of organizations in our data engage in contentious activities. Of the considered funding sources, funding from charities is more common (54%) than funding from authorities (36%). Overall, 60% of organizations are categorized as having high embeddedness, and 44% are highly professionalized, following the definitions provided earlier. A reform of the economic system is pursued by 33% of organizations.

3.3 | Models

On the basis of our theoretical framework, we tested the influence of different structural and organizational features on the way organizations attempt to hold corporations accountable. Our main focus was on both internal and external (albeit mediated through the organization) factors influencing the repertoires and aims of organizations. To test our hypotheses, we ran logistic regression models with the dependent variable capturing whether the organization included contentious modes of engagement in its repertoire (Hypotheses H1, H2, H5, H6) or whether the organization pursued a reform of the economic system (H3, H4). The focal predictors indicate whether the organization received funding from authorities (H1, H3), from charities (H2, H4), as well as the organization's degree of professionalization (H5) and embeddedness (H6).

4 | Findings

H1 and H2 deal with the effects of the type of funding on the organization's engagement in contentious modes of operation. We hypothesized that receiving funding from authorities or from charities reduces the probability of contentious modes of operation. We tested these hypotheses with a set of logistic regression models, presented in Table 3. According to Model C1, organizations that receive funding from state or government authorities are far less likely to engage in contentious activities (estimated probability of such engagement equals 0.16, 95% confidence interval (CI) = [0.10, 0.24]) compared to organizations that do not receive such funding (0.38, 95% CI = [0.31, 0.46]). This result supports H1. At the same time, as shown in the output of Model C2, organizations that receive funding from charities are

neither more or less likely to engage in contentious activities than organizations that do not receive such funding. This means that H2 is not supported. The coefficients for the effects of funding from authorities and charities on the choice of contentious modes of engagement remain substantively similar when controlling for other organizational characteristics (Model C5 in Table 3) and are also robust to controlling for the region of the organization's operation (Supporting Information Appendix A2), as well as to analysing different contentious activities (occupations and blockades, confrontational activities, demonstrative activities) separately (Supporting Information Appendix A1).

H3 and H4 address the effect of funding on an organization's aims, which we analysed with a logistic regression model presented in Table 4. We found a strong positive effect of receiving funding from charities on the probability of having economic reform among the organization's goals. On the basis of Model R1 in Table 4, organizations that received funding from charities have an estimated probability of pursuing economic reform of 0.42 (95% CI = [0.34, 0.50]), whereas for organizations without this funding source, the probability equals 0.22 (95% CI = [0.16, 0.30]). We also find an equally strong negative effect of receiving funding from authorities: Organizations that receive this kind of funding have an estimated probability of pursuing economic reform of 0.2 (95% CI = [0.13, 0.29]) compared to 0.4 (95% CI = [0.33, 0.47]) among organizations that do not receive such funding. These results are robust to including additional control variables (Model R2, Table 4 and Model M6 in Supporting Information Appendix A2).

H5 and H6 are about the effects of professionalization and embeddedness, on contentious modes of engagement. We tested these hypotheses with Models C3–C4 (see Table 3). Model C3 tested the effect of professionalization on contentious engagement, finding that organizations that are more professionalized are more likely to engage in contentious actions compared to those with a lower level of professionalization. An organization without any of the eight markers of professionalization, the probability of engaging in conscientious activities is 0.17 (95% CI = [0.11, 0.26]). In another organization, with all eight markers of professionalization, the probability is three times as high (0.52, 95% = [0.37, 0.67]). Thus, H5 is not supported, as the effect is statistically significant but in the opposite direction than expected. Model C4 estimates the effect of embeddedness on contentious activities, finding no significant effect, which means that H6 is also not supported.

5 | Discussion of Findings: What Enables or Impedes Civil Society in Their Struggle for CA

The most significant findings relate to funding and its impact on repertoires and aims to achieve desired goals. We found that organizations that receive funding from authorities—which accounts for the (partial) financing of more than 30% of organizations in our sample—are less likely to use contentious repertoires compared to organizations that do not rely on authorities for funding. Charity funding—which accounts for the (partial) financing of more than 50% of organizations in our sample—has no such effect. Further, we found that funding from authorities also decreases the likelihood that an organization will strive

TABLE 3 | Estimates from logistic regression models predicting the presence of contentious modes of engagement in an organization's repertoire.

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
Funding: Authorities	-0.947*** (0.296)				-1.347*** (0.334)
Funding: Charities		0.146 (0.258)			0.203 (0.309)
Professionalization (0–8)			0.208*** (0.065)		0.271*** (0.074)
High embeddedness				-0.129 (0.260)	-0.010 (0.279)
Constant	-0.551*** (0.152)	-0.927*** (0.192)	-1.567*** (0.268)	-0.771*** (0.199)	-1.461*** (0.317)
Log likelihood	-171.569	-176.990	-171.810	-177.028	-162.414
Akaike Inf. Crit.	347.137	357.981	347.621	358.056	334.829

Note: $N = 290$ organizations.

*** $p < 0.001$.

TABLE 4 | Estimates from logistic regression models predicting the presence of economic reform among the organization's aims.

	R1	R2
Funding: Authorities	-0.961*** (0.303)	-1.087*** (0.311)
Funding: Charities	0.934*** (0.285)	0.669** (0.302)
Professionalization (0–8)		0.165** (0.070)
High embeddedness		0.408 (0.275)
Constant	-0.919*** (0.200)	-1.537*** (0.317)
Log likelihood	-175.547	-171.870
Akaike Inf. Crit.	357.093	353.739

Note: $N = 290$ organizations.

*** $p < 0.001$.

** $p < 0.01$.

for a reform of the economic system, whereas charity funding increases this likelihood.

These results support the conclusions of Edwards and Hulme (1996), but not those in Banks et al. (2015) related to funding dependency created by charities. Contrary to Dauvergne and LeBaron's (2014) observations, we find that organizations that receive funding from charities have a higher propensity of pursuing economic reforms. However, charities are much more diverse

in terms of visions and aim than state authorities. Their grants are not exclusively channelled toward organizations involved in advocacy-related activities but also sponsor more movement-related initiatives (as is the case with Tides Foundation and Rosa Luxemburg Foundation, both in the donor top 20 in our sample). This is a qualitative difference compared to funding from authorities. In light of these results, we need to revisit the frequent claim in the existing scholarship regarding the similarities between funding from authorities and charity funding (see Section 2.2). Although funding from authorities clearly privileges low-conflict means of participation and negatively affects a receiver's propensity to pursue economic reforms, funding from charities does not have the same effect. This does not mean that charities do not seek to influence the behaviour, values and visions of recipients and prospective applicants. Quite on the contrary, numerous case studies have demonstrated that major charities use their resources, networks and reputation to steer applicants in the desired direction, and that the field of charities itself establishes funding and activity trends. The relationships between civil society actors and charities are, however, less clear cut than the relationships between civil society actors and authorities. Unlike state and government authorities, not all non-state funders have the capacity (or desire) to manage the behaviour of their grantees, and, unlike authorities, they are, at least potentially, in competition with other non-state funders (Gonzalez-Ocantos and Morcillo Laiz 2023). The effect of embeddedness and professionalization is one of many almost classic dilemmas in the field of (transnational or global) civil society and of social movement studies (Staggenborg 1988). Although some see the rise of professional organizations as positive developments (McAdam 1995; McCarthy and Zald 1973), others, such as Piven and Cloward (1977), contend that SMOs lose sight of their objectives, and that insurgency and disruption are the keys to

provoking change (p. 37). Our hypotheses about these two aspects of movement activity (H5 and H6) were not supported. We find no evidence that embeddedness impacts the likelihood of an organization making use of contentious repertoires. Additionally, contrary to our expectations, more professionalized organizations have a higher chance of using contentious repertoires, whereas we expected a negative effect. Nonetheless, it is worth noting that the field is populated by organizations that, for the most part, are not very contentious (Table 2). However, the fact that more professionalized organizations are the ones engaged in the ‘insurgency’ is curious in light of arguments brought forth by Piven and Cloward (1977) or more recently by both scholars of social movements and civil society (della Porta 2020; Yaziji and Doh 2009).

Our findings must be interpreted with respect to certain limitations (for a detailed discussion of the limitations of the data, see Section 3.1). One major limitation is related to the sampling strategy and the question of external validity. Our sample includes two network layers of four organizations. Apart from the initial four organizations, all others are listed as partners on their websites or on the websites of their immediate network. The sample represents the most visible expanded network of organizations active or connected to the field of CA, and, as such, we believe that the results are representative of (global) civil society—not only in the field of CA—when accounting for similar levels of visibility and detectability. The effect of professionalization, for instance, on less detectable organizations that are less prone to receiving funding might be different. Ideally, this research should be complemented by qualitative but comparative studies looking at smaller and less detectable organizations (notably grassroots organizations without an online presence). A second major limitation relates to measurement. The dataset includes only data that could be coded on the basis of the website content. We are cognizant that the reality of organizational life can differ from what is presented on a website. However, larger organizations that receive more funding, for instance, have incentives to present themselves in a way that conforms to reality in response to funding requirements, transparency rules, public attention and the like. Smaller organizations, with little or no funding (and little public attention), have fewer incentives to misrepresent their activities. A third limitation of the study is that we do not consider other factors external to the organization besides funding, such as the type of political regime, veto players or allies. The dataset we created contains geographical data and is suitable for an analysis of different contextual factors (e.g., the quality of democracy, GDP and associational density). Fourth, our data present a single snapshot in time and hence do not allow for estimating longitudinal effects of, for example, newly acquiring funding from authorities on the potential changes in the organization repertoires. Our claims to the causal nature of the associations we find are therefore limited.

6 | Conclusion

This article set out to identify impediments and obstacles to civil society in their struggle with corporations. Studying a large set of 290 organizations active in the field of CA, we identified impediments that are mainly external to the organizations themselves, although mediated by them. The article

shows how financial resources impact an organization’s choice of means *and* ends. The main findings include that funding from authorities impedes civil society action that is oppositional to power structures in both repertoires and aims. Although funding from charities does not have any significant impact on the means, it does impact the aims of organizations, and, unlike funding from authorities, it increases the likelihood of an organization’s advocacy for change. Conversely, high professionalization is a predictor of a contentious civil society. These results are relevant for the empirical study of civil society, CA initiatives and political participation, but also in terms of theory insofar as they confirm certain stable elements in the scholarship, such as the effect of funding, but refute others, such as specific funding situations and professionalized organization. The article draws on original data encompassing a large number of organizations. For the first time, the dataset used for this article offers a consistent source of information on a wide array of civil society actors active in or connected to the field of CA, including their operations and resources. The classification system for actors, repertoires and aims, which builds upon existing research, has the potential to become a foundational framework for future studies.

Our findings point to the need for clearer safeguards and governance mechanisms across all types of funding to prevent the instrumentalization of civil society and to ensure that support does not distort or narrow its transformative potential. All types of funding can be used to stimulate certain discourses rather than others and to focus civil society activity on certain social issues rather than others. It can also not be ruled out that funding is ‘politicized’, serving political interests of funding agencies or rich philanthropists. However, as our findings show, funding coming from authorities has the potential to mediate social conflict as it is clearly impacting an organization’s likelihood to make use of contentious repertoires. It also steers civil society activities away from demanding radical change, such as reform of the economic system. As our findings also show, charity funding has no influence on the repertoires of action. We did find, on the other hand, that organizations receiving charity funding have a higher probability to advocate for change (reform the economic system). The frequent political attacks on different civil society actors suggest a recognition of the transformative capacity of civil society supported by charities and philanthropic foundations. Such rhetoric can be interpreted as an attempt to delegitimize and constrain alternative agendas that challenge dominant power structures. Just as CA requires robust legal and political frameworks to ensure respect for human rights and the environment, so too does the funding of civil society require safeguards that protect its autonomy and integrity. Funders and organizations receiving funding need to operate in a legal framework that both allows and mandates transparency, protects pluralism and ensures that support does not become a tool for ideological capture or political repression. Public debates should shift their focus toward strengthening governance mechanisms that safeguard the autonomy of civil society and its capacity to challenge entrenched interests. Policymakers should recognize the influence of funding structures on organizational behaviour and create funding mechanisms that support diverse and transformative strategies while also assuring the integrity of civil society organizations. In turn, civil society actors should seek funding sources that not only align with their values and objectives but also preserve their independence and credibility. To

fulfil their democratic function, civil society organizations must resist becoming mere vehicles for particularistic interests and remain accountable to broader publics.

Yet, even with stronger governance mechanisms, the transformative capacity of civil society may remain constrained if structural limitations inherent to the political-economic system are not addressed. Our results raise a number of questions about the relationship between CA and the contemporary economic and legal system. Engaging in CA initiatives, while using the tools that the current legal, economic and political systems provide, can, at least potentially, have the opposite effect to what was intended. Corporations, similar to capitalist democracies, incorporate critique, as long as it does not demand structural change or use means that cannot be justified within the dominant discourse. The basic setup of the economic system and its legitimation through law seem to render CA initiatives worthless when using the playbook provided by the very targets of these initiatives (Baars 2018). Hence, initiatives that do not seek transformation and emancipation and that do not question the very essence of CA—the role corporations play and their focus on maximizing profits to the detriment of people and the environment—contribute to legitimizing and maintaining the system and the corporations themselves (Bader 2021; Baars 2018). The most obvious driver for this ‘colonization’ of the struggle for CA, and certainly many other fields, is funding from authorities. It impedes contentious repertoires—repertoires that are harder to incorporate into the hegemonic discourse—and it severely reduces the willingness of organizations to aim for a reform of the economic system. Funding from authorities thus constitutes the main impediment to seeking structural change with means other than those sanctioned by the democratic capitalist society.

Future research should explore how differences among charities and philanthropies shape civil society strategies. Running similar tests to those we performed, while drawing on a methodologically and theoretically sound grouping of charities (progressive or conservative; movement or advocacy-related; moderate or radical etc.) could bring more clarity in this regard. Our article also does not take into account the actual proportions of funding sources in organizations’ total budgets (due to limitations of the financial data available on organizations’ websites), and more detailed research on the weight of different funding types on organizational behaviour is welcome. Finally, although the article looked into important factors that have the potential to impede civil society’s capacity to advance solutions and to bring about relief, there are many others. Hence, more research on how the main veto players hamper civil society in their endeavour for CA and justice is welcome. Ultimately, understanding how funding structures and civil society interact with the logic of capital is essential to grasping both the limits and the capacities of collective action in confronting corporate power.

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Ethics Statement

This study adhered to all relevant ethical and legal principles.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

Data and materials are available at <https://doi.org/10.17632/pfp7zmxcyx.1>.

Endnotes

¹‘About’ sections and mission statements, the latter frequently used to analyze civil society organizations (Shibaïke et al. 2023) are, although oftentimes very polished, revealing, notably in conjunction with an analysis of annual reports, most of the aspects our analysis covers.

²Although all organizations were initially identified through a top-down network sampling approach (e.g., organizations that are listed as ‘partners’ or ‘network’ on the website of the respective hub-website), not all of them reciprocally listed partnerships or affiliations on their own websites. Our measure of embeddedness relies on whether an organization itself explicitly names partners or affiliations, rather than whether it was listed by others.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.

Supporting File 1: glob70024-sup-0001-Appendix.docx